

Anti-plasmodial and Hematological Effects of Methanol Leaf Extract of *Ficus capensis* in *Plasmodium berghei* Infected Mice

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Abstract

The plant *Ficus capensis*, traditionally used in treating ailments such as gonorrhoea, dysentery, and fever, has been underexplored for its potential antiplasmodial activity. This study evaluates the antiplasmodial efficacy and hematological effects of the methanol leaf extract of *F. capensis* on Swiss albino mice (*Mus musculus*) infected with *Plasmodium berghei* NK65. Peter's 4-day suppressive test was used to assess the anti-malarial activity following oral administration of the extract. Phytochemical screening identified the presence of terpenoids, flavonoids, tannins, steroids, saponins, and alkaloids, many of which have demonstrated bioactive properties in various biological activities. The extract exhibited a significant, dose-dependent reduction in parasitaemia, with 43.18%, 64.13%, and 78.16% suppression at 250 mg/kg, 500 mg/kg, and 1000 mg/kg, respectively ($p < 0.05$). The standard anti-malarial drug, chloroquine, significantly reduced parasitaemia to 0.37%, with a suppression rate of 96.33%. Hematological analysis indicated that the extract treatment increased Red Blood Cell count, hemoglobin levels, hematocrit, and platelet count, suggesting a protective effect against malaria-induced hematological disruptions. White blood cell (WBC) counts were elevated in parasitized groups but showed a dose-dependent decline in extract-treated mice, indicating a potential immune-modulating effect. These results collectively suggest that *F. capensis* holds considerable promise as a source of natural anti-malarial agents. It provides hematoprotective effects, which could offer a novel approach to treating malaria and its associated complications. Further studies are warranted to isolate the active compounds responsible for these effects and to evaluate their clinical applicability.

Keywords: Antiplasmodial, *Ficus capensis*, Hematological, Malaria, *Plasmodium berghei*

1.0 Introduction

Malaria is a life-threatening disease caused by *Plasmodium* parasites, with *Plasmodium falciparum* being the deadliest species [1]. In 2022, the World Health Organization reported 249 million cases and 608,000 deaths, with Africa bearing the highest disease burden [1] WHO estimates that 263 million malaria cases (95% CI 238 million to 294 million) occurred globally in 2023, equating to an incidence of 60.4 cases per 1000 population at risk, increasing from 58.6 cases per 1000 population at risk in 2022. 94% of all global cases in 2023 occurred in Africa, with 52%

of the global burden shared between just five African countries—Nigeria, DR Congo, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Mozambique [2]. Likewise, 95% of the estimated 597 000 global malaria deaths in 2023 were noted in the WHO African Region. The growing resistance of malaria parasites to standard drugs like chloroquine and artemisinin which significantly hampers the effectiveness of current treatments necessitates an urgent search for alternative treatments [2].

One hallmark of malaria infection is its impact on hematological indices, including anemia, thrombocytopenia, and alterations in white blood

cell counts [3, 4]. Malaria-induced hemolysis, bone marrow suppression, and immune-mediated destruction of blood cells contribute to severe complications, such as cerebral malaria and multi-organ failure [5]. Understanding these hematological disruptions is crucial for diagnosing malaria severity and evaluating the efficacy of potential therapeutic agents [5].

Given the challenges posed by drug resistance, medicinal plants have been explored as alternative anti-malarial agents. Historically, compounds such as quinine and artemisinin were derived from plants [6, 7]. Phytochemicals—including alkaloids, flavonoids, and terpenoids—have demonstrated antiplasmodial activity by disrupting parasite metabolism and reducing oxidative stress [8, 9].

Ficus capensis (sometimes referred to as *Ficus sur*), a member of the Moraceae family, is widely used in traditional medicine across Nigeria and Sudan [10]. According to Gills [11] and Ayinde and Owolabi [12], the plant is referred to as "uwaryara" in the Hausa language, "opoto" in the Yoruba language, "rima bichehi" in the Fulani and "obada" in the Edo language. Ethnobotanical reports indicate its use in treating fevers, dysentery, gonorrhoea, and anaemia, suggesting potential anti-malarial properties [11, 13, 14]. Previous studies have identified alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, and terpenoids in their extracts, which are known for their pharmacological activities [15]. However, its antiplasmodial effects and impact on hematological indices remain underexplored.

This study evaluated the antiplasmodial efficacy of the methanol leaf extract of *Ficus capensis* in Swiss albino mice infected with *Plasmodium berghei* NK65. Additionally, we assessed its effects on Red Blood Cell (RBC) count, hemoglobin levels, hematocrit, White Blood Cell (WBC) count, and platelet count to determine its potential role in mitigating malaria-induced hematological disruptions.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Plant Collection and Authentication

Fresh leaves of *Ficus capensis* were collected based on traditional healers' claims of their efficacy in treating malaria in Southern Nigeria. The leaves of the plant were obtained from Uwasota, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria in the month of June 2023.

A Botanist authenticated them in the Department of Plant Biology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Benin, Nigeria. Voucher specimens of the plant with code number UBHF₃₃₁ were deposited at the Herbarium section of the department for future reference.

2.2 Preparation of Plant Extract

Fresh leaves of *Ficus capensis* were air-dried in the laboratory. The dried pieces were then hand-crushed, and 500g of the crushed material was extracted by soaking in 2.5 litres of methanol for 72 hours. After that, they were filtered using a double-layered muslin cloth into a clean conical flask. The filtrates were concentrated using a rotary evaporator and stored at 4°C in an airtight container until further use [16].

2.3 Phytochemical Screening

The methanol leaf extract of *F. capensis* was screened for the presence of flavonoids, cardiac glycosides, reducing sugars, tannins, saponins, terpenoids, anthraquinones and steroids using the methods reported by Shemishere *et al* [17].

Healthy Swiss albino male mice weighing 18-30g were obtained in the month of July 2023 from the Nigerian Institute of Medical Research (NIMR), Lagos State, Nigeria and were used for the experiment. The mice were housed under standard laboratory conditions at a temperature of 27±2°C, relative humidity of 70% and 12 hr day/night cycles. They had free access to grower mash and water. The animals were allowed to acclimatize for two weeks before commencing the experiment. The experiments were conducted strictly with internationally accepted principles for laboratory animals' use and care as contained in the Canadian Council on Animal Care Guidelines and Protocol Review [19].

2.4 Acute Oral Toxicity Study (Median Lethal Dose)

The acute toxicity of the plant extracts were determined by establishing its median lethal dose (LD₅₀) using the Lorke method [18]. The test was carried out in two phases.

Phase I: Nine (09) mice were divided into three groups (A, B, and C) of three mice each. The three groups were administered orally with graded

concentrations (10, 100, and 1000 mg/kg body weight) of leaf extracts of the plant. For 48 hours, the animals were monitored for signs of toxicity, such as tremors, weakness, loss of appetite, and even death. The observation was continued for seven days.

In the phase 2 experiment, nine (09) mice were divided into three groups (A, B, and C) of three mice each. The three groups were administered orally with doses of 1600, 2900 and 5000 mg/kg body weight of the extracts respectively

All the animals were monitored for 48 hours for pain, distress, behavioural alterations, and, most importantly, death. The observation was continued for the next 14 days.

2.4 Experimental Animals

Healthy Swiss albino male mice weighing 18-30g were obtained from the Nigerian Institute of Medical Research (NIMR), Lagos State, Nigeria in the month of July 2023 and were used for the experiment. The mice were housed under standard laboratory conditions at a temperature of $27\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, relative humidity of 70% and 12 hr day/night cycles. They had free access to grower mash and water. The animals were allowed to acclimatize for two weeks before commencing the experiment. The experiments were conducted strictly with internationally accepted principles for laboratory animals' use and care as contained in the Canadian Council on Animal Care Guidelines and Protocol Review [19].

2.5 Inoculation of Animals

Mice infected with *Plasmodium berghei* NK65 chloroquine-sensitive strain were obtained from the Nigerian Institute of Medical Research (NIMR) Lagos, Nigeria in the month of July 2023 and kept at the animal house in the Department of Biochemistry, University of Benin, Edo State, Nigeria. A volume of 100 μL of parasitized erythrocytes was obtained from donor-infected mice by cardiac puncture and made up to 3mL with normal saline. The animals were inoculated intra-peritoneally with 0.2 mL of the blood containing about 10^7 infected erythrocytes [20].

2.5 Experimental Design

Mice numbering forty-eight (48) were randomly divided into six groups (n = 8 per group):

Group 1: Normal control (non-parasitized, non-treated)

Group 2: Negative control (*P. berghei*-infected, non-treated)

Group 3: Positive control (*P. berghei*-infected, treated with chloroquine 10 mg/kg)

Group 4: *P. berghei*-infected, treated with *F. capensis* extract (250 mg/kg)

Group 5: *P. berghei*-infected, treated with *F. capensis* extract (500 mg/kg)

Group 6: *P. berghei*-infected, treated with *F. capensis* extract (1000 mg/kg)

2.6 Antiplasmodial Studies (Suppressive Test)

Peter's 4-day suppressive test against chloroquine-sensitive *Plasmodium berghei* NK 65 infection in mice was employed [20, 21]. The mice (48) were randomly divided into six groups. Three (3) groups with eight mice were the control groups, while three groups of 8 were the test groups. On the first day of the experiment ('day 0'), all mice were injected intra-peritoneally with *Plasmodium berghei* NK 65 infected erythrocytes, except the non-parasitized, non-treated group mice.

Two hours after the infection of mice, the uninfected control (non-parasitized, non-treated, group 1) and the negative control (parasitized, non-treated- group 2) were given 0.5ml carboxyl methyl cellulose (CMC- 0.7%). The positive control (group 3) received 10mg/kg chloroquine. The three test groups were given 250mg/kg, 500mg/kg and 1000mg/kg of methanol extracts of *F. capensis* for groups 4, 5 and 6, respectively. All administration was done orally using a gavage and this was done for four consecutive days ('day 0- day 3').

On 'day 4' of the experiment, blood was collected from the tails of the mice and smeared onto a microscopic slide to make a thin film [22]. The blood films were allowed to dry, fixed with methanol (100%), and stained with Giemsa (10%) for 10 minutes. The stained films were then washed

with phosphate buffer, pH 7.2, and allowed to dry [23].

The slides were then examined microscopically using $\times 100$ magnification in oil immersion [24]. The parasitemia was determined by counting at least eight fields per slide with a minimum of 100 red blood cells (RBC) per field. The percentage parasitemia was calculated using the modified Peter and Robinson [23] formula:

The percentage parasitemia was expressed as mean \pm SEM. The average suppression of parasitemia was calculated by comparing the average percentage parasitaemia in each group with that of negative control using the formula of Abosi and Raseroke [25]:

Where A = Average percentage suppression of parasitaemia

B = Average percentage parasitaemia in the negative control group

C = Average percentage parasitaemia in the test group

2.7 Haematological assays

Haematological assays were done using the methods reported by Alum *et al.* [26].

2.7.1 Samples Collection and Assays

On day 5 of the experiment, animals were fasted overnight and sacrificed by cervical dislocation. Samples were then collected. Blood was collected from the abdominal aorta and the heart via a syringe into plain sterile bottles and EDTA tubes (for haematology analysis). Blood samples inside the plain tubes were allowed to stand for 30 minutes to clot and centrifuged at 1,000g for 10 minutes at room temperature to obtain serum.

2.8 Statistical Analysis

All results were expressed as mean \pm SEM. A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Dunnett's test was used to determine the significance of the differences between the groups. Statistical significance was declared when the p-value was less than 0.05. The statistical analysis used the graph pad prism (version 5.04).

3.0 Results

3.1 Acute Toxicity Study

The oral administration of a single dose of the *F. capensis* methanol extracts, at different concentrations, to mice did not cause any visible signs of toxicity. No mortality was recorded at all doses used up to 72 hours after oral administration. The median lethal dose (LD₅₀) of the extracts was estimated to be $> 5,000$ mg/kg body weight for *F. capensis*.

3.2 Phytochemical constituents of methanol extract of *F. capensis* leaves

The phytochemical screening results of *F. capensis* leaf extracts (Table 1) showed the presence of cardiac glycosides, terpenoids, alkaloids, reducing sugars, steroids, flavonoids, tannins and saponins. However, anthraquinones were absent.

Table 1: Phytochemical present in the methanol extract of *Ficus capensis* leaves

Phytochemicals	<i>Ficus capensis</i> leaf
Cardiac glycosides	++
Terpenoids	++
Alkaloids:	
Wagner's	+
Dragendroff	++
Reducing sugars	++
Flavonoids	++
Tannins	+++
Saponins	++
Steroids	++
Anthraquinones	-

KEY: +: trace amount, ++: moderate amounts, +++: high amounts, -: absent

3.3 Results for Suppressive Test

Table 2 presents the percentage of parasitaemia and the percentage of suppression for each group of methanol extract of *F. capensis* leaf in albino mice. Significant ($p < 0.05$) dose-dependent reduction of parasitemia was observed in all groups of mice treated with the plant extract when compared with the negative control PnT (parasitized, non-treated). The PnT (Parasitized, non-treated) group had the highest parasitemia at 10.12%, serving as the baseline with 0% suppression. The standard antimalarial drug, chloroquine, had the lowest percentage of parasitaemia (0.37%) and the highest level of parasite suppression (96.33%).

In the *F. capensis* treated groups, the percentage suppression increased with an increase in extract concentration (250mg/kg, 500mg/kg and

1000mg/kg doses produced suppression of 43.18%, 64.13% and 78.16%, respectively).

Table 2: Antiplasmodial effects of methanol leaf extract of *Ficus capensis*

Group	% Parasitemia	% Suppression
nPnT	0.00	0.00
PnT	10.12 ± 1.31 ^e	0.00
Chloroquine	0.37 ± 0.22 ^a	96.33
<i>F. capensis</i> (250 mg/kg)	5.75 ± 0.31 ^d	43.18
<i>F. capensis</i> (500 mg/kg)	3.63 ± 0.54 ^c	64.13
<i>F. capensis</i> (1000 mg/kg)	2.21 ± 0.49 ^b	78.16

Where nPnT = Non parasitized, not- treated, PnT = Parasitized, non- treated.

Values are mean ± SEM (n = 6). Values bearing the same superscript are not significantly different, while those bearing a different superscript are significantly different ($p < 0.05$).

3.4 Hematological Results

The WBC counts in the non-parasitized group ($8.55 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$) were significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower than those of the parasitized groups (plant extract and chloroquine-treated groups), except for the parasitized mice treated with chloroquine, which had the lowest levels of WBC ($5.60 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$) (figure 1). There was also a dose-dependent decline in WBC counts for the extract-treated groups (WBC counts for 250mg/kg, 500mg/kg and 1000mg/kg extract-treated groups were $24.30 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, $19.95 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$, and $18.14 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ respectively).

The RBC counts, haemoglobin and haematocrit levels for the non-parasitized mice were

significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than those of the parasitized groups (figure 2). The plant extract-treated groups and chloroquine-treated groups had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher levels of these parameters when compared with the parasitized, non-treated (PnT) group.

The platelet count for the non-parasitized group was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than those of the parasitized groups, except for the parasitized, chloroquine-treated group. The plant extract at 250 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg doses significantly increased the platelet count when compared with the parasitized non-treated group (250mg/kg and 500mg/kg doses had platelet counts of $537.00 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ and $494.50 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ respectively, while PnT group had platelet counts of $465.50 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$).

Figure 1: Effect of *F. capensis* Extract on WBC (day 5)

Where nPnT= non-parasitized, non-treated; PnT= parasitized, non-treated; CQ = Chloroquine treated. FC = *Ficus capensis* treated. Values are expressed as Mean \pm SEM (n = 8) of triplicate analyses. Bars with different lowercase letters represent significant differences between means at $p < 0.05$ using Graph Pad Prism statistical package version 6.

Figure 2: Effect of *F. capensis* Extract on RBC (day 5)

Where nPnT= non-parasitized, non-treated; PnT= parasitized, non-treated; CQ = Chloroquine treated. FC = *Ficus capensis* treated. Values are expressed as Mean \pm SEM (n = 8) of triplicate analyses. Bars with different lowercase letters represent significant differences between means at $p < 0.05$ using Graph Pad Prism statistical package version 6.

Figure 3: Effect of *F. capensis* Extract on HGB (day 5)

Where nPnT= non-parasitized, non-treated; PnT= parasitized, non-treated; CQ = Chloroquine treated. FC = *Ficus capensis* treated. Values are expressed as Mean \pm SEM (n = 8) of triplicate analyses. Bars with different lowercase letters represent significant differences between means at $p < 0.05$ using Graph Pad Prism statistical package version 6.

Figure 4: Effect of *F. capensis* Extract on HCT % (day 5)

Where nPnT= non-parasitized, non-treated; PnT= parasitized, non-treated; CQ = Chloroquine treated. FC = *Ficus capensis* treated. Values are expressed as Mean \pm SEM (n = 8) of triplicate analyses. Bars with different lowercase letters represent significant differences between means at $p < 0.05$ using Graph Pad Prism statistical package version 6. $p < 0.05$ using Graph Pad Prism statistical package version 6.

Figure 5: Effect of *F. capensis* Extract on PLT (day 5)

Where nPnT= non-parasitized, non-treated; PnT= parasitized, non-treated; CQ = Chloroquine treated. FC = *Ficus capensis* treated. Values are expressed as Mean \pm SEM (n = 8) of triplicate analyses. Bars with different lowercase letters represent significant differences between means at $p < 0.05$ using Graph Pad Prism statistical package version 6.

4.0 Discussion

This study investigated the efficacy of methanol extracts from *Ficus capensis* leaves, focusing primarily on their anti-malarial and hematoprotective properties.

The phytochemical constituents identified in the methanol extract, including flavonoids, tannins, steroids, terpenoids, and alkaloids, are well-known for their bioactive properties and have been previously documented for their anti-malarial activities [27]. The study's findings align with existing literature regarding the role of phytochemicals in malaria treatment. Previous studies have demonstrated that plants rich in phenolic compounds, such as flavonoids and tannins, exhibit significant anti-malarial and hematoprotective effects. These compounds work

through various mechanisms, including direct parasiticidal activity, modulation of immune responses, and protection against oxidative stress [28].

Flavonoids have been reported to exert antiplasmodial effects through multiple mechanisms. These include inhibiting hemozoin formation, disrupting redox homeostasis, and interfering with parasite metabolic pathways [29]. By preventing hemozoin formation, flavonoids inhibit the detoxification of free heme, leading to parasite toxicity. Additionally, their antioxidant properties help modulate oxidative stress, which is crucial for parasite survival [30].

Alkaloids have been shown to interfere with *Plasmodium* DNA synthesis and protein metabolism, potentially disrupting essential cellular

functions. Some alkaloids exhibit direct interactions with DNA, leading to parasite growth inhibition, while others interfere with enzymatic processes necessary for replication [31].

Tannins contribute to the extract's antiplasmodial effects by inhibiting parasite enzyme activity. Their ability to bind proteins and interfere with metabolic processes makes them potent anti-protozoal agents [32]. Tannins may also exert immunomodulatory effects, enhancing the host's defense mechanisms against infection. These mechanisms likely contribute to the observed anti-malarial effects of *Ficus capensis* extract [33].

Identifying steroids and saponins in the extract further supports its anti-malarial efficacy. Steroids are known for their immune-modulatory effects, potentially enhancing the body's ability to fight malaria infections. On the other hand, Saponins possess antiprotozoal properties, disrupting the cell membranes of parasites and leading to their destruction [33, 34]. Saponins also have the ability of precipitating and coagulating red blood cells. Other characteristics of saponins include development of foams in aqueous solutions, hemolytic activity, cholesterol binding properties, and antimicrobial activity [35, 36]

The results of an earlier study conducted by Omoregie and Okugbo [37] demonstrated that the *in vitro* antioxidant activity of methanol extracts of *D. edulis* and *F. capensis* leaf varies. The extract of *D. edulis* exhibited a higher free radical scavenging capacity, ferric reducing power, and flavonoid content. In contrast, the extract of *F. capensis* exhibited a higher proanthocyanidins and phenolics content. Certain phytochemicals, including flavonoids, tannins, proanthocyanidins, cardiac glycosides, and terpenoids, in these plant leaves may be responsible for the antioxidant activity of the extracts. Previous studies have also demonstrated the antiplasmodial properties of phytochemicals such as terpenoids, flavonoids, alkaloids and tannins [38]. Consequently, *F. capensis* and *D. edulis* may function as potential natural antioxidant sources that could aid in the prevention of the progression of a variety of oxidative stress-related diseases, such as malaria [38].

The study evaluates the effectiveness of *F. capensis* methanol leaf extract and chloroquine in reducing parasitaemia and their overall suppressive impact on Plasmodium infection in mice. The results show that the extract possesses significant anti-malarial activity, with the 1000 mg/kg dose showing a suppression rate comparable to established anti-malarial drugs like chloroquine. The chloroquine-treated group showed a higher suppression rate (96.33%). Still, the extract's dose-dependent efficacy, especially at 1000 mg/kg (78.16% suppression), suggests it could be a valuable complementary or alternative therapeutic option for malaria. The moderate parasitaemia levels observed in the *F. capensis* -treated groups (compared to the untreated group) further support its potential use in treating malaria. Further studies are required to isolate the active compounds and optimize dosing for maximum efficacy. The chloroquine-treated group significantly reduced parasitaemia to 0.37%, with a suppression rate of 96.33%. This result reflects chloroquine's potent anti-malarial action, as a standard drug used in malaria treatment. The suppression rate of nearly 96% suggests that chloroquine effectively inhibits Plasmodium growth and reproduction, leading to the near-total elimination of the parasite from the host. The dose-dependent nature of the response suggests that multiple active constituents work synergistically to inhibit the growth and proliferation of *Plasmodium* parasites. Although the active compound has not been identified, the antiplasmodial activity observed in this study could likely result from the combined effect of these compounds. Earlier research has also indicated that methanol leaf extracts of *F. capensis* possess antiplasmodial activity in mice models [39].

The safety profile of *F. capensis* methanol leaf extracts was evaluated, showing no visible signs of toxicity or mortality at any dose. The estimated median lethal dose (LD50) was greater than 5,000 mg/kg body weight, indicating a relatively safe profile at tested doses. This suggests the extract as a potential candidate for further studies, consistent with Eluka et al.'s earlier work [39].

Malaria parasites exert oxidative stress within the parasitized RBCs during the conversion of heme (ferroprotoporphyrin) to hematin (ferriprotoporphyrin) and through immune system activation, which causes the release of reactive oxygen species (ROS) [40]. Plasmodium infection may increase WBCs as the immune system combats

the infection, which explains the significantly higher WBC levels in the parasitized groups (except for the chloroquine-treated group) compared to the non-parasitized control. The parasitized groups also showed significantly lower RBC, Hb, and HCT levels than the non-parasitized control.

The hematological analysis provided further insights into the therapeutic potential of *F. capensis* extracts. Malaria typically induces significant hematological alterations, such as anemia, leukocytosis, and thrombocytopenia. The untreated parasitized group (PnT) showed elevated WBC counts, indicative of an acute inflammatory response to malaria infection. In contrast, the extract-treated groups displayed a dose-dependent normalization of WBC counts, suggesting an anti-inflammatory effect of the extract [41].

The RBC counts, hemoglobin levels, and hematocrit values were significantly higher in the extract-treated groups compared to the PnT group. This suggests that *F. capensis* extract not only combats the parasitic infection but also mitigates malaria-induced anemia. The hematoprotective effect is likely due to the presence of flavonoids and other phenolic compounds, which are known to enhance erythropoiesis and protect against oxidative stress-induced hemolysis [42].

Moreover, platelet count analysis revealed a significant increase in the extract-treated groups, particularly at the 250 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg doses. This is critical, as thrombocytopenia is a common and severe complication of malaria [43]. The ability of *F. capensis* extract to normalize platelet counts suggests its potential to prevent malaria-associated bleeding disorders and enhance overall hematological stability.

Conclusion

The study reveals that *Ficus capensis* methanol leaf extract has significant anti-malarial and hematoprotective properties. The extract contains bioactive compounds like flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, steroids, and saponins, known for their antiparasitodal and immune-modulatory activities. It suppresses parasitaemia dose-dependently, comparable to chloroquine, and shows promising hematoprotective effects, normalizing WBC, RBC, hemoglobin, and platelet counts. The acute toxicity study supports the extract's safety, with no visible signs of toxicity and an estimated LD50 greater

than 5,000 mg/kg body weight. These results collectively suggest that *F. capensis* holds considerable promise as a source of natural anti-malarial agents. It provides hematoprotective effects, which could offer a novel approach to treating malaria and its associated complications. Further studies are warranted to isolate the active compounds responsible for these effects and to evaluate their clinical applicability.

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